

Tunneling Fundamentals, Practice and Innovations

Annual Short Course

Special Session on University Transportation Infrastructure

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Blast Vulnerability of Drop Ceilings in Roadway Tunnels

Students: Ziyang Ouyang, Aerik Carlton

Faculty: Clay Naito, Spencer Quiel

Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering
Lehigh University

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Intro: Blast Threats and Effects

Bomb Threat Stand-Off Distances

Threat Description		Explosives Capacity ¹ (TNT Equivalent)
	Pipe Bomb	5 LBS/ 2.3 KG
	Briefcase/ Suitcase Bomb	50 LBS/ 23 KG
	Compact Sedan	500 LBS/ 227 KG
	Sedan	1,000 LBS/ 454 KG
	Passenger/ Cargo Van	4,000 LBS/ 1,814 KG
	Small Moving Van/ Delivery Truck	10,000 LBS/ 4,536 KG
	Moving Van/ Water Truck	30,000 LBS/ 13,608 KG
	Semi-Trailer	60,000 LBS/ 27,216 KG

LOCAL DAMAGE

Intro: Tunnel Liner Study

- Tunnel Cross-Section Inventory
- Prototypes for Blast Assessment

- A – 500 lbs TNT Equivalent
- B – 1000 lbs TNT Equivalent
- C – 2000 lbs TNT Equivalent

Bai, F., Guo, Q., Root, K., Naito, C., Quiel, S., "Blast Vulnerability Assessment of Road Tunnels with Reinforced Concrete Liners," Journal of the Transportation Research Board, Manuscript Number: 18-05880, August 2017, Accepted March 2018, Published online September 28, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0361198118798458>

Intro: Drop Ceilings

- Drop Ceilings
 - Different Failure Mechanism
 - Design for Downward Loads Only
- Explosive Charge Sizes
 - 50 lbs TNT Equivalent
 - 100 lbs TNT Equivalent
 - 500 lbs TNT Equivalent

From clarage.com

Research Objectives

- Quantify the blast resistance of drop ceiling panels in tunnels and examine the cost effectiveness of retrofit strategies compared to removal.

Scope of Work

- Conduct numerical analysis of prototypes based on two tunnels in service
 - Circa-1960 Construction
 - Circa-1970 Construction
- Quantify blast demand for accidental detonation at 2 ft above the road surface at the center of the roadway:
 - 50 lbs TNT Equivalent
 - 100 lbs TNT Equivalent
 - 500 lbs TNT Equivalent
- Map expected damage based on demands

Case Study – Representative Tunnels w/ Drop Ceilings

• Tunnel 1

- Length: 1000 ft (305 m)
- Area: 820 ft² (77 m²)
- Height: 19.3 ft (5.9 m)
- 3-Lane Traffic
- Continuous flexural reinforcement

• Tunnel 2

- Length: 3600 ft (1100 m)
- Area: 400 ft² (38 m²)
- Height: 14 ft (4.3 m)
- 2-Lane Traffic
- Discontinuous flexural reinforcement

Methodology

- ProSAir → Blast Demand
- Structural Analysis → Resistance
- SDOF Analysis → Dynamic Response

PDC-TR 06-08
Revision 1
7 January 2008

U.S. ARMY CORPS OF ENGINEERS
PROTECTIVE DESIGN CENTER
TECHNICAL REPORT

Single Degree of Freedom Structural Response Limits for Antiterrorism Design

DISTRIBUTION STATEMENT A: Approved for Public Release;
Distribution is unlimited.

Blast Demands

Resistance Assessment

Full Span with Buckled Hangers

Case A - Upper Bound

Case B - Middle Bound

Case C & D - Lower Bound

Case	Bound	Length of Span	B. C.
Case A	Upper	11.0 m (36.0 ft)	pin-pin
Case B	Middle	11.0 m (36.0 ft)	pin-fix
Case C	Lower	2.0 m (6.5 ft)	pin-fix
Case D	Lower	3.5 m (11.5 ft)	fix-fix

Vulnerability Assessment of Ceiling Panels

Table 4-1 Response Limits for Reinforced Concrete ¹

Member		B1		B2		B3		B4	
		μ	θ	μ	θ	μ	θ	μ	θ
Flexure	No shear reinforcing/ without tension membrane	1	-	-	2°	-	5°	-	10°
	With compression face steel reinforcing and shear reinforcing/without tension membrane ²	1	-	-	4°	-	6°	-	10°
	With tension membrane (L/h>=5) ^{3,4}	1	-	-	6°	-	12°	-	20°
Combined Flexure & Compression ⁵	No shear reinforcing/ without tension membrane	1	-	-	2°	-	2°	-	2°
	With compression face steel reinforcing and shear reinforcing/without tension membrane ²	1	-	-	4°	-	4°	-	4°
Compression ^{5,6}	Walls & Seismic Columns	0.9	-	1	-	2	-	3	-
	Non-Seismic Columns	0.7	-	0.8	-	0.9	-	1	-

Damage maps – 500 lbs

Damage Key

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Damage Maps – Tunnel 1

100 lbs TNT: 35% of tunnel ceiling has **Moderate Damage**

50 lbs TNT: 100% of tunnel ceiling has **Little to No Damage**

Damage Key:

- Fail
- Heavy Damage
- Moderate Damage
- Little to No Damage

Damage Maps – Tunnel 2

50 lb TNT : 78% **Ceiling Loss**
 100 lbs TNT: 100% **Ceiling Loss**

Recommendations

- Remove Drop Ceilings
- Hanger Retrofit
- FRP Retrofit

Tentative Cost of Removing Ceiling Panels
(scaled to prototype tunnel size based on PennDOT
information provided for Squirrel Hill and Fort Pitt
Tunnels)

- Tunnel 1: \$ 2,308,000
- Tunnel 2: \$ 6,283,000

Squirrel Hill Tunnel

From Gannettfleming.com

Fort Pitt Tunnel

From TRIBLIVE.com

Ventilation System in Tunnels

- Portal to Portal
- Shaft to Shaft
- Portal to Shaft

Recommendations

- Removing Drop Ceilings
- Hanger Retrofit
- FRP Retrofit

Damage Key:

Recommendations

- Removing Drop Ceilings
- Hanger Retrofit
- **FRP Retrofit**
 - Cost of FRP Retrofit
 - Tunnel-1: ??
 - Tunnel-2: ??

UNDER
DEVELOPMENT

Summary and Conclusions

- Impulse and Pressure vs. Area and Standoff Distance
- Resistance Function: Simplified Cases vs. FE Model
- Blast Resistance
- Vulnerability: Drop Ceilings vs. Tunnel Liners
- Blast Resistance vs. Boundary Condition
- Removing Drop Ceilings
- Hanger Retrofit
- FRP Retrofit

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